

SCHOOLS
AS LIVING
LABS

SALL

A useful summary outlining a concrete approach to science education programs by promoting collaboration between schools and local communities, utilising the living-lab methodology to facilitate a transformation in the European educational landscape

The SALL Project brings the powerful **CONCEPT** and **METHODOLOGY** of **LIVING LABS**

The SALL Project has adopted the concept of **OPEN SCHOOLING** in **SCIENCE EDUCATION** where schools become agents of community well-being by creating new partnerships with other local actors and addressing local issues relevant to them.

Our conceptualization of a **LIVING LAB** involves: The collaboration among different societal actors who wish to deal together with a certain problem or issue which is important to each one of them.

This includes:

- 1 THE CO-CREATION OF IDEAS TO SOLVE THE PROBLEM OR ISSUE
- 2 THE DEVELOPMENT OF BASIC ELEMENTS OF THE ENVISIONED SOLUTION FAST AND ECONOMICALLY (PROTOTYPING)
- 3 THE TESTING OF THE SOLUTION WITH THE STAKEHOLDERS TO GET FEEDBACK AND FINALISE OR IMPROVE IT

SALL PROPOSES TO TRANSFORM SCHOOLS INTO LIVING LABS

This methodology has been widely tested and has proved to be capable of nurturing meaningful collaborations between actors with diverging interests but with common objectives.

Together, they build new products, new services, new uses, etc. through a cycle that typically comprises:

SALL BRINGS TOGETHER SCHOOL COMMUNITIES, INCLUDING:

- Teachers
- Students, and their families
- Research institutions
- Policy-makers
- Science engagement organisations and other non-formal learning
- Open innovation spaces

More than 400 school communities across 10 countries implement the SALL LIVING-LAB Methodology to address local issues linked to the food system.

1

**SCIENCE
LEARNING
DIALOGUES**

A wealth of opinion exchanges, discussions and reflections which have taken place during the whole project since its start.

2

EVALUATION

YEAR 2

127 SALL school projects
(implemented by 125 schools)

YEAR 3

174 SALL school projects
(implemented by 150 schools)

485
TEACHERS

184
MEMBERS
OF THE SCHOOL
ADMINISTRATION

1697
STUDENTS

200
SOCIETAL
ACTORS

3

AIMING TO PROVIDE ANSWERS TO THE FOLLOWING QUESTIONS

What are the broad recommendations and policy objectives for policymakers, researchers, and civil society organisations that are meaningful to accelerate the take-up of living-lab-based open schooling?

What is the anticipated impact of these changes on each policy domain and society?

Which major policy gaps and challenges should be considered and addressed for normalising the implementation of living-lab-based open schooling?

What kind of instruments and incentives are necessary to tackle these challenges?

Which actions should be put in place in order to implement such recommendations and related policy objectives?

4

LESSONS LEARNED

Collection of
SALL – SCHOOLS AS LIVING LABS
lessons learned that can be
featured and highlighted.

